

OPTIMAL OPERATION OF MULTIPLE AND MULTI PURPOSE RESERVOIRS SYSTEMS USING NON-DOMINATED SORTING GENETIC ALGORITHM (NSGA-II)

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ABSTRACT

Iran is considered an arid country with rainfall less than a third of the average rainfall in the world. In these areas, one of the strategies to cope with water shortages and drought is to use optimal operation models. Several studies have been conducted in this area and a variety of models have been suggested in order to optimization and simulation of operation of the reservoirs. The latest method used in this field, based on Pareto Front is multi-objective genetic algorithm NSGA-II. In this paper, NSGA-II multi-objective genetic algorithm was used to solve the proposed multi-objective optimization model for two-reservoir system of Ostor and Pirtaghi dams in Ghezel Ozan catchment. The aims of the study are to maximize revenue from the sale of energy produced by power plants and also flood control storage volume of the reservoir under study in wet months in order to control probable flood. The system consists of two consecutive reservoirs on Ghezel Ozan River which in this model, based on a certain amount of water released from the plant during the project (decision variables), the most appropriate model will be obtained for reservoir operation of dams, storage volume of the reservoir for flood control, The optimal allocation to power plants and finally revenue from the sale of energy produced. The final results of the problem have provided several optimal ways which are not superior to each other (set of Pareto optimal solutions). The decision maker is able to find the best answer by considering the situations of the present problem and by applying different methods of deciding.

KEYWORDS:

NSGA-II, Multi-objective optimization, Pareto solutions, Flood Control, Hydropower.

INTRODUCTION

Optimal finding is very important and essential particularly in complex problems. Basically, the process of the optimal finding is finding the total values of vector of design variables that lead to an optimal value for the objective function. There are many mathematical methods which use the gradients for solving the optimal point. Although there are fundamental flaws in the gradient-based methods that one of them is the need in some methods for an initial guess which leads to be trapped in local optimal points. This problem led to the development of evolutionary algorithms.

Genetic Algorithm is an efficient method to solve the multi-objective problems. Ability of genetic algorithms for simultaneously search on different regions of solution space makes it possible to find different answers for problems with non-convex, discontinuous and multi-model decision space. The first multi-objective algorithm, called the Vector Evaluated Genetic Algorithm (VEGA) proposed by Schaffer in 1985 [1]. Since then, researchers have started to investigate in this field and different methods have been made with different capabilities in this area. The following methods can be mentioned as examples [2]: Multi Objective Genetic Algorithm (MOGA) [3, 4], Niche Pareto Genetic Algorithm (NPGA) [4], Random Weighted Genetic Algorithm (RWGA) [5], Non Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA) [6], Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm (SPEA) [7], Pareto-Archived Evolution Strategy (PAES) [8], SPEA2 [9], Fast Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) [10], Rank-Density Based Genetic Algorithm (RDGA) [11] and Multi-objective evolutionary algorithm (MEA) [12].

Regarding to comparison of multi-objective evolutionary algorithms, research done by Zitzler & Deb (2000) can be mentioned that they have carried out a comparison between different methods like Random Search Algorithm (RAND), Fonseca and

Feleming's Multi-Objective EA (FFGA), NPGA, Hajela and Lin's Weighted-Sum Based Approach (HLGA), VEGA, NSGA, Single-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm using weighted-sum aggregation (SOEA), and SPEA. Results showed that Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) perform much better than random search methods (RAND) and among the evolutionary algorithms, SODA, SPEA, NSGA methods will provide more appropriate answers due to Pareto optimal solutions space [13].

Reddy & Kumar [14] used Multi-Objective Differential Evolution (MODE) approach and NSGA-II method to optimize the single reservoir system. The results showed that NSGA-II method leads to Pareto optimal space with an appropriate convergence and it has the ability that to be used in the optimization of water resources systems. Field [15] studied multi-objective optimization operation of Folsom reservoir in America. Targets in a single-reservoir system are: to minimize the cost of delivering water and to maximize the production of hydroelectric energy. An evolutionary model of genetic algorithm NSGA-II and a one-dimensional hydrodynamic thermal model were used to optimize the aims.

In recent years, good research has been done for optimizing the operation of reservoirs by the NSGA-II algorithm. Some objectives of the mentioned researches are: water supply and flood control [16], operating rule curves for cascade hydropower reservoirs [17], balances ecological protection and human needs [18], management of conjunctive use of surface and groundwater [19], and so on.

Reviewing the former studies shows that the application of NSGA-II is limited on the two reservoir systems. Therefore, the aim of this study is to optimize the multi-objective and multi-reservoir water resources in Ghezel Ozan basin. The objectives are to maximize the benefits from hydropower production and to optimize the storage of reservoir for flood control in the wet months of the year.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

NSGA-II. The NSGA-II algorithm consists of following steps:

1. Randomly produced parent generation P_0 in N numbers.
2. Classifying the first generation of the parents based on non-dominated solutions.

3. Considering an appropriate order with non-dominated level for each non-dominated solution (1 for the best level, 2 for the next best level after 1 and etc).

4. Offspring reproduction Q_0 in N numbers by using the selection, crossover and mutation operators.

5. Considering the first reproduction, which is consisted of parent and offspring chromosomes, the next reproduction is as follow:

- a. Composition of parent P_t and offspring Q_t chromosomes, and reproduction R_t in $2N$ numbers.

- b. Classifying R_t generation based on non-dominated method of sorting and identification of non-dominated fronts (F_1, F_2, \dots, F_t).

- c. Parent reproduction for the next iteration P_{t+1} , using produced non-dominated fronts in N numbers. In this stage, due to the number of required chromosomes for the parent generation N . At the beginning the first front chromosomes for the parent generation is chosen, and if this number of chromosomes are not enough for the total number of required chromosomes for the parent generation, then they are harvested step by step from 2, 3 and... fronts until it reaches the total number of N .

- d. Applying crossover operators, mutation on the regenerated parent generation P_{t+1} and regenerating the offspring generation in N numbers.

- e. Repeating step 5 to achieve the total number of iterations.

Continuity constraints of the reservoir are the most important constraints dominating the problem. In other words the procedure of this algorithm is shown in the flowchart below (Figure 1):

Case study. Ghezel Ozan basin has been Between East longitude $46^\circ -27'$ to $51^\circ -6'$ and Northern Latitude 35° to $37^\circ -56'$ Branches of the river's watershed come from near city Qorveh in Kurdistan province at 2000 m height and move to the North. The area under study in this research is the distance between Ostor dam to Pirtaghi dam. Figure 2 has provided the location of branches of Ghezel Ozan catchment and the dams under study in this catchment [20]. Meteorological data (water surface evaporation, precipitation) and hydrology (surface water potential) are collected from previous studies [21]. The specifications of Ostor dam and Pirtaghi dam is given in Table (1). Also schematic of the optimization problem is shown in Figure 3.

FIGURE 1
Genetic algorithm with non-recessive sorting of solutions

TABLE 1
Specifications of reservoirs and power plants

The specification of reservoirs with abbreviation form	Ostoor dam	Pirtaghi dam
Dead Storage (S_{dead})	91.8 MCM	98 MCM
Minimum Operation Level (S_{op})	94.4 MCM	100 MCM
Live Storage (S_n)	2495 MCM	827 MCM
The maximum storage (S_{max})	3000 MCM	930 MCM
minimum required water in downstream of reservoir (MDT)	44.85 MCM	66.96 MCM
Diameter of penstock (D)	1.38m	1.40m
The net height difference (DH)	12m	6m
The minimum amount of water released from the reservoir (R_{min})	0 m ³ /sec	0 m ³ /sec
The maximum amount of water released from the reservoir (R_{max})	40 m ³ /sec	50 m ³ /sec
Plant factor (PF)	0.25	0.25
Turbine efficiency (η)	0.60	0.60

FIGURE 2
Location of branches Ghezel Ozan catchment and the dams under study [22]

FIGURE 3
Schematic of the two reservoir system [23]

According to Figure 3, system consists of two consecutive reservoirs which in downstream of each dam, there is a hydroelectric powerhouse which get its require water from its upstream reservoirs. The above model has been performed for a period of twelve months which has started from October and

will finish in September. In this research number 1 represents Oostor dam reservoir and number 2 indicates Pirtaghi dam reservoir. The average monthly values of the input discharge, rainfall and evaporation of reservoirs are shown in Tables 2 to 4 respectively.

TABLE 2
The average mounthly input discharge to reservoirs

	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep
I1	17.90	38.40	43.10	42.10	48.00	92.80	225.90	232.70	76.60	13.20	2.70	4.10
I2	11.10	24.25	26.15	25.65	29.65	56.20	143.05	146.95	49.20	8.50	2.20	2.85

TABLE 3
The average evaporation amount from the reservoirs

	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep
E1	134.9	68.3	64	63.8	48	75	91.5	139.5	200.5	252.5	256	228.8
E2	136	84.3	48.6	34.7	42.7	59.5	90.5	125.9	166.2	210.7	220	207

TABLE 4
The average precipitation amount on the reservoirs

	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep
P1	17.7	31.5	21.5	36	34.7	36.3	43.7	57.5	26	7.4	4.2	4.8
P2	18	32	21.9	36.6	35.3	37	44.5	58.5	26.5	7.5	4.3	4.9

IMPLEMENTATION

Objective functions. The proposed model has two objective functions in this paper that are in conflict with each other. With respect to the NSGA-II multi-objective optimization algorithm is to find the objective function minimum, therefore, the proposed objective function of the optimization model in this plan will be as follows:

$$f(1) \rightarrow \max F(1) = \text{Maximize } \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^T pwp^t * PE_i^t \quad (1)$$

$$f(2) \rightarrow \max F(2) = \text{Maximize } \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^T c^t * (S_i^n - S_i^t) \quad (2)$$

Where f (1): The first objective function (to maximize revenue from electricity generation) and f (2): To maximum volume control probable floods. n is the number of the reservoirs under study (Equal to 2), T is Time duration for Operating Model (12 months), pwp^t : Selling price of a unit of energy produced in month t by Rails on megawatt hours, c^t Flood constant factor which is equal to 1 in the flood months and is 0 in other months. S_i^n is reservoir volume at normal level in the reservoir i per cubic meter and S_i^t is Volume of reservoir i at the beginning of month t per cubic meter and PE_i^t is generated Energy at reservoir i and month t by Watt which is obtained from the following equation:

$$PE_i^t = \eta_i^t * \gamma * R_i^t * H_i^t * PF_i * d_i * 24 \quad (3)$$

Where η_i^t is turbine efficiency in power plant of reservoir i in month t that it is a function of the ratio of head to maximum head, γ is specific

weight of water which is equal to 9806 (N/m³), R_i^t is the amount of water released into powerhouse for producing energy from reservoir i in month t based on cubic meters per second, H_i^t is pure water head above turbine by meter which is equal to impure water load minus the head loss, PF_i is performance Coefficient of powerhouse reservoir i, d_i is number of days in each month of the year, R_i^t , the amount of water released into powerhouse for producing energy f_i is the only unknown variable of the problem in above equations and other variables can be measured (calculated).

Constraints of the Model. Water Balance in Reservoirs: Water balance in the reservoirs under study is defined based on the continuity equation as follows:

$$S_1^{t+1} = S_1^t + I_1^t + P_1^t - E_1^t - R_1^t - Spill_1^t \quad (4)$$

$$S_2^{t+1} = S_2^t + I_2^t + I_3^t + P_2^t - E_2^t - R_2^t - Spill_2^t \quad (5)$$

Number 1 represents Ostor dam reservoir and number 2 indicates Pirtaghi dam reservoir and the number 3 represents Sangurchai River. S_i^t and S_i^{t+1} are the volume of water stored in the reservoir (m) at the beginning and end of period t in reservoirs 1 and 2, respectively, I_1^t and I_2^t are river discharge input to reservoir 1 and 2 respectively in month t, P_1^t , P_2^t are the rate of rainfall in the reservoir 1 and 2 respectively in month t, E_1^t and E_2^t are the rate of evaporation from the reservoir area 1 and 2 in month t, R_1^t and R_2^t are the rate of output of the plant's water reservoir 1 and 2 in month t. $Spill_1^t$ and $Spill_2^t$ are the

rate of overflow water from the reservoir 1 and 2 respectively in month t . I_3^t is Sangurchay River input to reservoir 2 in month t .

The volume of evaporated water from each reservoir and the volume of water causing by rainfall on reservoirs are related water reservoir area. Reservoir water storage restricted to the maximum volume of reservoir per period S_{\max} and dead storage S_{dead} [24].

$$S_{dead} \leq S_t \leq S_{\max} \quad (6)$$

Water release constraints: The amount of water input into powerhouse will increase between powerhouse operation levels to reservoir normal level with changes of the head.

$$R_{\min} \leq R \leq R_{\max} \quad (7)$$

Where R_{\min} and R_{\max} are the minimum and the maximum amount of water released from the reservoir 1 and 2 to the powerhouse in terms of cubic meters per second respectively. R_{\min} is equal to 0 in this problem. But in order to calculate R_{\max} discharge relationship is used

$$R = C_d A \sqrt{2gH} \quad (8)$$

Where C_d is flow Coefficient which is equal to 0.6 [25], A is cross section area of penstock and H is head of pure water above turbine.

Minimum environmental flows: To protect the environment, a minimum flow in the river, or in other words downstream of the dams, is required. Thus, the total power output of water and overflow water must meet minimum needs of downstream. This constraint is defined as follows:

$$R_i + Spill_i \geq MDT_i \quad (9)$$

Where MDT_i is the minimum required water in downstream of reservoir i in terms of cubic meters, respectively.

Penalty functions. Three penalty functions are considered for this problem. These functions are related to physical facts that:

- The water volume of reservoir should not be less than dead storage volume (S_{dead}).
- The amount of water release (R_t) should not be less than minimum release (R_{\min}).
- The amount of released water should not be less than minimum required flow. This is to protect environmental issues in tail water.

If these constraints are not restored, a penalty function is applied for both reservoirs as follows:

$$P_s = \sum_{t=1}^T (1 + k [S_t - S_{dead}]^2) \quad (10)$$

$$P_R = \sum_{t=1}^T (1 + k [R_t - R_{\min}]^2) \quad (11)$$

$$P_{MDT} = \sum_{t=1}^T (1 + k [R_t + Spillway_t - MDT]^2) \quad (12)$$

Optimization begins with an initial population of 20 persons. First, initial population is simulated and their fitness function is determined (parent population), then, parents are put two by two in 15 mating pool. Selecting two by two (as a race choice) or the amount of mating pool which are often half of the initial population can vary. Then, based on dominance rank and fitness between both parents have been put in one pool, crossover and mutation operator have been taken place in two by two of them. All amounts related to the implementation of the program are shown in Table (5).

TABLE 5
Type and the coefficients of the operators used in the program

NSGA-II parameters	Type
Type of reproduction and its possibility coefficient:	SBX , 0.9
Type of mutation and its coefficient:	Polynomial, 0.1
Crossover distribution parameter :	3
Mutation distribution parameter:	50
Mutation probability ($P_{mutation}$):	0.1
Crossover probability ($P_{crossover}$):	0.9
Type of operator selection:	Tournament
Stopping condition of algorithm :	Achieving to maximum number of reproduction

RESULTS

Pareto Front. Due to the fact that from months February to April which are considered the wet months of the year, the model has two objectives in conflict, NSGA-II algorithm model performed by defining two objective functions. After trial and error, the number of determined generations in the model has been set equal to 400 generations. In Figure 4 shows the optimal points of Pareto resulting from optimization and program execution in two-dimensional form, the meaning of non-domination has shown very well which is formed the basis of Operator NSGA-II. In the figure, the negative horizontal axis is revenue from sale of hydroelectric energy and the negative vertical axis is flood control volume in the reservoirs.

According to the Figure 4, by increasing “f1” value, the amounts of storage for flood control volume is greater and by moving to the left side of the Pareto chart, profit the amounts of hydroelectric energy reaches to maximum in the reservoir. So it is possible by considering this process and according to the proposed problem requirements and based on current conditions in the area and the importance of each objective, a Pareto optimal point is chosen that there is a compromise between the two objectives. Selecting the best answer totally depends on the design of decision makers’ opinion.

FIGURE 4
The generated Pareto front by the NSGA-II optimization model (20 points in shape, is equal to the number of initial population.)

The Water Height in the Reservoirs. Due to the Figure 5, water height in reservoirs 1 and 2 is lower in wet months of years than other months of the year. The reason is that because the sole purpose is to maximize energy production and revenue from the sale of energy in 8 non-wet months of the year, the model developed in order to maximize water height and reservoir volume in these months, but in wet months of the year, the other purpose is also added to the above mentioned purpose, that is, to maximize flood control storage volume. Therefore, Water height is reduced in the reservoir, so that both the objective function will be optimized.

FIGURE 5
the water height variation in Ostoor and Pirtaghi reservoirs

FIGURE 6
the water release in Ostoor and Pirtaghi reservoirs

The Rate of Release of Each Reservoir during the Period. The rate of the current release of the reservoir to produce hydroelectric energy into related powerhouse is shown in Figure 6. As it can be seen, the amount of water released into powerhouse in the reservoir 2 is more than in reservoir 1. It is for this reason that First, the height of the reservoir 2 is more than reservoir 1 and also penstock diagonal and flow rate is more than reservoir 1. In Figure 7, the flood release rate is the maximum in flood months because of optimizing the second objective function of the problem, the model by increasing the amount of release, tries to keep the reservoir empty for flood control and vice versa.

Installed capacity and energy production of each powerhouse during the period. If we plot the changes of the installed capacity and energy production of each on a graph over time, Figure 7 and 8 will be obtained. Installed capacity depends on several hydraulic parameters. To calculate Installed

capacity of the powerhouse, the following formula is used.

$$I.C = \frac{\eta * \gamma * Q * H}{1000} \quad (13)$$

The I.C is the installed capacity of the powerhouse that is based on KW (Installed capacity is nominal capacity of units of a powerhouse) and Q is released discharge to the powerhouse through its penstocks. The other parameters have already been introduced. After calculating installed capacity, it is possible to calculate the monthly energy production of powerhouse within a month per kW by using equation 14.

$$E = I.C * PF * d_i * 24 \quad (14)$$

Where E is the monthly energy production per kW, PF: The plant factor that for both powerhouses has been considered 25%, this means that the powerhouse works 25% of the clock which is equivalent to 6 hours.

FIGURE 7
The variation of installed capacity in Ostoor and Pirtaghi reservoirs

FIGURE 8
the monthly energy production of power plant in Ostoor and Pirtaghi reservoirs

According to Figures 7 and 8, it can be said energy production has reduced in flood months in comparison with the other months in the year; the reason is to keep the reservoir empty in the months to control probable floods, so required height has been reduced for turbine performance and consequently energy production.

Reservoirs' Losses. Casualties of reservoirs include evaporation from the reservoir level and overflow water from each reservoir. As expected, with regard to the relationship level, there was no overflow in the reservoir 1, because reservoirs are

large due to water needs for energy production, but in the reservoir 2 overflow was only done at the eleventh and twelfth months. The reason can be enter flow of Sangchur River between the reservoirs 1 and 2 that makes there is overflow from reservoir 2 during the eighth, ninth and tenth periods. The water has never overflowed from reservoir 1 at any time. But if there is overflow from reservoir 1, the excess water is controlled and is transported to reservoir 2. According to the water balance equation, the overflow water from the reservoir 2 is related to late of the months of May, June and July.

TABLE 6
Energy per unit sales price and total revenue in reservoirs 1 and 2

	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep
Energy price per MWh (RLS)	46000	46000	46000	44000	44000	44000	49000	49000	49000	57000	57000	57000
Total revenue in Ostoor reservoir (million Riyal)	149.9	180.7	170	161.9	106.7	105.5	165	199.6	34.58	311.1	371.4	291.8
Total revenue in Pirtaghi reservoir (million Riyal)	403.2	420.5	490.8	466.7	299.9	311.2	438.5	577.1	736.1	774.8	797.7	714.6

TABLE 7
Total water stored in reservoirs 1 and 2 in wet months (MCM)

	Ostoor Reservoir	Pirtaghi Reservoir	Total storage
Feb	2617.45	550.68	3168.13
Mar	2697.25	481.32	3178.57
Apr	2368.67	373.69	2742.36
May	1840.3	32.58	1872.88
Total	9523.67	1438.27	10961.94

Optimal state is the state which by considering effective parameters to maximize the objective functions, the amount of water released to the plants happens in such a way that on the one hand, the appropriate volume of the reservoir is considered to control probable floods in the flood months of the year and on the other hand the income of hydroelectric power production reaches the maximum rate. Due to the rising cost of electricity in the summer months, if only energy production is considered, it is better to store water during the flood months of the year and it will be sold at higher prices in the summer months. However, because of having the objective function, namely, volume storage of the reservoir for flood control, this goal is in conflict with the primary purpose; Therefore, a compromise can be used between these two functions.

According to the results by using NSGA-II method, in this project, income can be achieved through selling price per unit of energy produced times total energy generated in each powerhouse. In the powerhouse related to the reservoir 1, the highest revenue is related to August which is equal to 371 and 38 Millions of Rials and the lowest revenue is related to March which is equal to 105.53 million Rials (Figure 9). The highest and lowest revenue occurs in the months of August and February in the reservoir 2 respectively and their value is equal to 797.70 million Rials and 299.88 million Rials, respectively (Table 6).

Regarding the second objective function, namely, to maximize the storage volume in the reservoir in wet months in order to control probable floods must be said that the volume of the reservoir will be kept empty in order to control probable floods in each of the reservoirs 1 and 2 in the months of February to May (Table 7). According to Table 3, total volume of flood control storage in flood months and in two reservoirs under study during the project period which is equivalent to the value of the second objective function, it is 10.96 billion cubic meters In multi-objective genetic algorithm NSGA-II.

CONCLUSIONS

By observing and analysing the results of this method, it can be concluded that multi-objective genetic algorithm NSGA-II was administered to a small number of generations and the good values of the objective functions achieved by finding the optimal point. Another distinct advantage of this method is much less running time than other genetic algorithm methods which is an important factor in the performance of computer systems and saving time. One of the important factors for not trapped in a local optimum point, can be noted to mutation operator and proper distribution of the population which the multi-objective genetic algorithm NSGA-II has a very good performance because of having the crowded distance while selection and population diversity will keep very well in different generations while program performing.

The next advantage of Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm NSGA-II is using of encoding real numbers instead of encoding binary or the numbers zero and one which using of actual encoding has several advantages; such that, the problem space searching level which are encoded in the way of true values by mutation operator in chromosome is higher than the values which are encoded in binary mode and will provide better solutions. In this way, we do not convert to binary mode, values precision will not be reduced because of that. It does not need to be decoded and requires less time and memory. Mutations can be adjusted so that the mutation rate is decreased by increasing of population convergence, encoding with real numbers can limit mutations to small changes and crossover operator can be convergent to get the right answer. The chromosome encoding method is more complicated, mutations will be also performed better.

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